

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Sehgal, S., Tomar, R., Mehta, D., & Kumar, S. (2026). Enhancing learning and evaluation: AI as a catalyst for sustainable education. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 30(2), e250118. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2026250118.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Sehgal, S., Tomar, R., Mehta, D., Kumar, S., & Gomes, G. R. S. (2026). Peer review report for: Enhancing learning and evaluation: AI as a catalyst for sustainable education. RAC. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19444459>

REVIEWERS:

- Glauco Ricardo Simões Gomes (Universidade Nove de Julho and Universidade Estadual de Montes Claros, Brazil)
The other reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Glauco Ricardo Simões Gomes

Date review returned: September 22, 2025

Recommendation: Major revision

Comments to the authors

Agradeço pela oportunidade de avaliar este manuscrito. O artigo traz contribuição relevante ao investigar o uso de IA em processos de avaliação, dialogando com o ODS-4. O tema é atual, de interesse para a comunidade e bem apresentado.

Contudo, identifiquei pontos que precisam ser fortalecidos antes da publicação:

Incluir métricas estatísticas robustas (MAE, RMSE, ICC, Bland-Altman) além da variação exata;

Explicitar a confiabilidade interavaliadores humanos;
 Disponibilizar os prompts completos, rubricas detalhadas e dados em anexo ou repositório;
 Modular a linguagem do claim de “equivalência” e alinhar as conclusões às evidências;
 Incluir análise exploratória de vieses e avaliação mais estruturada das justificativas geradas.

Esses ajustes aumentarão a robustez metodológica, a clareza e a reprodutibilidade do estudo. Reitero que vejo potencial de publicação após revisão substancial.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: Nenhum

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 3. Average

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 3. Average

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Authors' Responses

Reviewer 1

Comment 1 - Added Mean absolute error & Bland–Altman plots in section 3, 4 and 5. The same is included in section 3,4, and 5 highlighted in yellow

Comment 2 - The main claim of the paper lies in the AI-based evaluation with Human-based evaluation and not the inter-human comparison. Justification is given in the paper

Comment 3 - Prompts are added to the Appendix, The data supporting the findings of this study cannot be made publicly

available due to privacy and confidentiality considerations involving the participants. As the dataset contains sensitive information specific to the students involved, sharing it could compromise their anonymity. Therefore, the data are not included in any public repository or appendix.

Comment 4 - We have removed the word "equivalence". This study indicates that AI-enabled evaluation can be implemented as an alternative to traditional human grading, hence facilitating the attainment of SDG 4. It is included in the Section 6, conclusion and highlighted in yellow

Comment 5 - A bias analysis is not conducted in this study, as the language models were solely tasked with evaluating students' responses and assigning scores based on predefined criteria. The focus of the study is on assessing the models' evaluation capabilities, rather than their text generation abilities. Since the models did not produce original content or interact beyond scoring, conducting a bias analysis was not applicable or relevant to the scope of this study Justification given in the paper.

Comment 6 - All suggestions are taken due care and incorporated in the paper and highlighted in yellow.

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Glauco Ricardo Simões Gomes

Date review returned: December 14, 2025

Recommendation: Accept

Comments:

A título de melhoria, o artigo poderia reforçar como sua abordagem associa-se ao ODS 4 de forma mais efetiva.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: None

Rating:

Interest: 1. Excellent

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 1. Excellent

Overall: 1. Excellent

Authors' Responses

There is no author's response for this round